

STRENGTH AND RESPONSE OF FILAMENT WOUND MOTOR CASE SUBJECTED TO INTERNAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced composites are widely used in many fields. One notable application is the filament wound motor case for solid rocket under high internal pressure. Therefore, predicting the mechanical response and strength of it is extremely important. In this investigation, we employed the model which consists of a structural analysis for calculating the global response, a failure analysis for predicting local damage of the structure and making the stiffness degradation for the damaged elements. A nonlinear finite element code based on the Total Lagrangian formulation was developed for the model. To verify the model, experiments were also conducted. An excellent agreement was found between the computer simulations and the tested results.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites are now widely accepted as structural materials within the aerospace, automotive and sporting goods industries. Especially with the filament wound motor case for solid rocket under high internal pressure, Glass/Epoxy, Carbon/Epoxy and Kevlar/Epoxy got utilized. Hence, its structural analysis are essential.

Based on Kirchhoff theory or Reissner's shell theory, an analytical method for determining the structural response of a pressure vessel subjected to internal pressure was presented in Ref. 1 or Ref. 2. As for geometrically behavior, Idelsohn⁽³⁾ analyzed a spherical wound tank and the composite head of a rocket motor using classical shell elements. Assuming a parabolic shear stress distribution in the thickness coordinate, a geometrically nonlinear shear deformation theory for laminated cylindrical pressure vessel was given by Dennis⁽⁴⁾. Numerical results were obtained for a laminated cylindrical pressure vessel with use of nonlinear shell elements. But there are few papers in analyzing the filament wound motor case with use of three-dimensional solid elements because the calculated work is much astonishing, especially considering the effects of geometrically nonlinear behavior. However, three-dimensional solid element analysis can give higher analytical precision to composite structures and make use of the stiffness degradation model in damaged elements. Axisymmetrical solid element analysis were employed from design point in this paper.

The strength of composite pressure vessels and damage in the structures as a re-

sult of the applied loads can be predicted by a set of failure criteria, such as the Maximum Stress failure criterion^(5,6) and Tsai-Wu failure criterion⁽⁷⁾

Ref. 5 also pointed out that the model which concerns the effect of process of structural damage is essential to composite structures while compared with the metal ones. That model is the most rational method for the analysis of composite structures. Unfortunately, it was not usually employed in the engineering. In structural analysis, the simply way to handle the process of structural damage of composite is to employ the model with the stiffness degradation of damaged elements. The model for stiffness degradation proposed by Ref. 5 was also adopted in this paper.

In this paper an investigation was performed to study the response and strength of filament wound motor case subjected to internal pressure. The geometrically nonlinear finite element method was employed and the effect of structural damage and stiffness degradation of damaged elements was considered. The model is also capable of predicting the residual stiffness and strength of the motor case after a proload. An excellent agreement was found between the numerical results and the experimental data. It is expected that the method of this paper can be extended to other filament wound motor cases.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS THEORY

Since filament wound motor case could undergo substantial out-of-plane deformation before catastrophic failure occurred, the analysis was based on the large deformation theory. Consider an elastic body with the original configuration v_0 which deforms to the current configuration $v_n(q + \Delta q)$ from the previous configuration $v_{n-1}(q)$. The equilibrium in the variational form at the current step, in terms of the original configuration v_0 , can be described as equation(1)

$$\int_{v_0} \delta \bar{E}_{ij} \cdot \bar{S}_{ij} dv = \int_{v_0} \delta \bar{u}_i \cdot \bar{P}_{oi} dv + \int_{A_{oi}} \delta \bar{u}_i \cdot \bar{q}_{oi} dv \quad (1)$$

where \bar{S}_{ij} and $\delta \bar{E}_{ij}$ are Kirchhoff's stresses and the variational parts of Green strains at the current time in terms of the original configuration, respectively. \bar{P}_{oi} and \bar{q}_{oi} are the body forces and the surface forces at the current time in terms of the original configuration, respectively. $\delta \bar{u}_i$ is the variational part of displacement at the current time in terms of the original configuration.

$\bar{S}_{ij}, \bar{E}_{ij}, \bar{u}_i$ can expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{ij} &= S_{ij} + \Delta S_{ij} \\ \bar{E}_{ij} &= E_{ij} + \Delta E_{ij} \\ \bar{u}_i &= u_i + \Delta u_i \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where S_{ij}, E_{ij}, u_i are the Kirchhoff's stresses, Green strains and displacement at the previous time in terms of the original configuration, respectively. $\Delta S_{ij}, \Delta E_{ij}$ and Δu_i are the incremental ones at the step from q to $q + \Delta q$.

Therefore

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta \bar{u}_i &= \delta(\Delta u_i) \\ \delta \bar{E}_{ij} &= \delta(\Delta E_{ij}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Substituting equation (2), (3) into equation (1), we obtain the governing equations for finite elements separating.

$$\int_{V_0} \delta(\Delta E_{ij}) \cdot (S_{ij} + \Delta S_{ij}) dv = \int_{V_0} \delta(\Delta u_i) \cdot \bar{P}_{oi} dv + \int_{A_{oi}} \delta(\Delta u_i) \cdot \bar{q}_{oi} dv \quad (4)$$

where

$$\Delta S_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \cdot \Delta E_{kl} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta E_{ij} &= \Delta e_{ij} + \Delta \eta_{ij} \\ \Delta e_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} (\Delta u_{i,j} + \Delta u_{j,i}) \\ \Delta \eta_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} \Delta u_{k,i} \cdot \Delta u_{k,j} \\ (i, j, k &= 1, 2, 3) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

C_{ijkl} is the tangent stiffness for elastic material and depend on the damaged condition of composite structure.

Equation (4) can be solved by a nonlinear finite element method provided that both ply orientation and boundary conditions (displacements and forces) are specified properly. Furthermore, damage could propagate much more extensively in composites than in metals. As a consequence, the local damage could have a significant effect on the global response of the structure. Hence, the local-global interaction effect has to be taken into account in the analysis. Accordingly, the structural analysis and the proposed failure analysis have to be evaluated simultaneously.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

1) Failure criterion

Damage in the filament wound motor case as a result of the applied internal pressure will be predicted by a set of failure criteria. In this investigation, the Maximum Stress failure criteria were selected for predicting the element failure and its failure modes. They consist of the following divided criteria.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 < X_L & \quad \text{for longitudinal tensile failure} \\ \sigma_1 > X_C & \quad \text{for longitudinal compress failure} \\ \sigma_2 < Y_L & \quad \text{for transverse tensile failure} \\ \sigma_2 > Y_C & \quad \text{for transverse compress failure} \\ \sigma_{12} < S & \quad \text{for shear failure} \end{aligned}$$

where X_L, X_C, Y_L, Y_C, S are the respective strength value which were tested by single direction test of the composite.

At each incremental step, failure criteria were applied from element to element to predict failure and to determine the corresponding failure mode. This information is necessary for calculating the degree of degradation of the mechanical properties within the damaged area and the subsequent response of the Structure as a result of the damage.

2)Property Degradation Model

Once damage occurs,material properties in the damaged area degenerate. The degree of property degradation strongly depends on the failure mechanism. Hence,based on the failure mode,a property degradation model similar to Ref. 5 was proposed.

For both transverse tensile and compress failure.

$$E_2 \rightarrow 0, \quad \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23} \rightarrow 0$$

and for longitudinal tensile and compress failure or shearing failure.

$$E_2 \rightarrow 0, \quad \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23} \rightarrow 0$$

$$\frac{E_1^d}{E_1} = \frac{G_{12}^d}{G_{12}} = 0.3$$

where E_1^d, G_{12}^d are the reduced tensile and shear moduli, respectively.

**NUMERICAL SOLUTIONS AND ITS
COMPARISION WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA**

For the problem of the structural analysis of filament wound motor case,the axisymmetric finite element method about large deformation was employed. The damage process was introduced and the stiffness degradation of damaged elements was received. The numerical results of that model were compared with the experimental data.

Fig. 1 shows the structure of some filament wound motor case of solid rocket. The elements were divided along the thickness direction of the case. The structure includes the case of Kevlar-49/Epoxy, Al-alloy cover and skirt, and the rubber layer between the case and the cover.

Fig. 2a) and 2b) were the longitudinal and the round strains of the outer surface of the dome respectively, while the internal pressure was 6.0 Mpa. An excellent agreement was found between the calculated results and the experimental data. Yet, the compressive band on the dome near the cylinder was obvious, just like in the experiment.

Fig. 3a) and 3b) were the longitudinal and the round strains of the outer point at the middle of the cylinder at different internal pressure, respectively. Also an excellent agreement was found. Furthermore, it revealed that the response of the cylinder varied linearly along the internal pressure.

Fig. 4a) and 4b) were the longitudinal and the round strains of some tested point on the dome at different internal pressure, respectively. It revealed that. ① linear analysis is not available ② nonlinear analysis accompanying failure analysis give higher analytical precision than without failure analysis.

In this investigation, the strength calculation were also given. The motor case will burst at the middle part of the cylinder under the internal pressure of 8.0 Mpa. The experiment told us that the motor case bursted also at the middle part of the cylinder under the internal pressure of 7.7 Mpa. Therefore, the calculated value of strength by the model of this paper was also in an excellent agreement with the experimental data.

Fig. 1 structure of some solid rocket

Fig. 2a) longitudinal strains of the outer surface of the dome at 6.0 Mpa

Fig. 2b) round strains of the outer surface of the dome at 6.0 Mpa

Fig. 3a) longitudinal strains of the outer point at the middle of the cylinder under different loads

Fig. 3b) round strains of the outer point at the middle of the cylinder under different loads

Fig. 4a) longitudinal strains of some tested point on the dome under different loads

Fig. 4b) round strains of some tested point on the dome under different loads

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this investigation, an analytical model was developed for predicting the strength and response of filament wound motor case of solid rocket undergoing large deformation subjected to internal pressure. Furthermore, we concluded for filament wound motor case of solid rocket that

- (1) finite element analysis of large deformation are essential.
- (2) Structural analysis with failure analysis are the most rational method, which can give the most satisfactory results.

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